

D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.1

**Protocol for Crop sampling
and
Laboratory Operating Procedure (LOP)**

[Compartment 4]

**Version 1
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Protocol for Crop sampling and Laboratory Operating Procedure (LOP)

A. Description

Compilation of sampling crops compartment and points, and further laboratory analysis, ensuring harmonization of testing procedures, which will enhance comparability of the results obtained from different regions of Europe and among compartments. Complete crops (roots, stalk, ears and leaves) will be used. This protocol will allow answering to the different questions from the FED-AMR project.

B. Equipment and material

- Sampling stick / spear
- Sealable plastic bag for 500 g sample
- Sterile scissors (to trim long material if necessary)
- Freezer and deep freezer
- Oven
- Disposable half-mask respirator approved to EN149 standard
- Laboratory gloves
- Thermostatically controlled bath
- Sieve
- Balance
- Sterile disposable wooden spatula
- Centrifuge
- Filtration system (for bacteriology of water)
- Containers for contaminated materials
- Sterile propylene flasks, 50ml
- Sterile cryotubes

C. Procedure

1. Sampling, transportation and conservation

- In each field of the four fields with crops (C1 to C4), complete plants are selected randomly. For each plant, roots, stalk, ears and leaves will be collected and analysed independently but the sampling unit will be the plant. Sample identifiers (see sample reference in section “D”) will be given per sampling unit, specifying the part of the plant.
- Take a picture of each extraction point and capture the GPS coordinates, and collect meteorological conditions and information on the soil characteristics (moisture, pH, % clay, % sand, % humus).
- Each crop sample might weight about **2.0 kg**.

- Sample containers should be suitable for preserving the sample integrity avoiding any changes or effects from moisture, temperature or light. The sample container should be sterile, of suitable size to allow storage of sufficient sample to complete all determinations required and there should be some air space left once filled (in order to avoid leakage and to allow effective mixing prior to sampling for all tests required in the laboratory). The container should have a securely fitting lid and should be uniquely identified with a sample identifier on the container and not the lid. As samples will be also examined microbiologically it should be handled under sterile conditions to preserve the microbiological load.
- Transportation of the samples to the laboratory shall ensure that they are kept under conditions which will minimize any alteration in the microorganisms present.
- Identify samples clearly and completely, and record the sample information.
- Storage conditions should be cautious as it alters composition, matrix interactions, chemical and/or enzymatic activity, thus should be followed the conservation indicated (that is 0°C to 5°C).
- Testing shall begin on the day of receipt of samples or on the first working day afterwards (to avoid the loss of eDNA), which allows the method to be completed in accordance with the respective protocol.
- If exceptionally, testing is not to begin on the day of receipt, the samples must be stored in accordance with the appropriate protocol (0° to 5°C, in the dark).
- If samples have been refrigerated before testing they should be removed to room temperature (18-21°C) for a minimum of 1 hour prior to the start of the procedure.
- Samples should be stored in such a way that no cross contamination can occur with other diagnostic samples.
- All the steps for sample preparation should be done rather quickly, under convenient and very clean conditions so there could be no degradation of sensitive analytes, no contaminations and no oxidation process due to influences of too high temperatures, daylight, air or from residues of apparatus used or from samples prepared before or simultaneously.
- Stability of parameters in this context refers only to influences of sample preparation (e.g. intensive grinding):
 - Trace elements (e.g. Cu, Zn, Mn, Fe, Se, Co) and heavy metals (e.g. As, Pb, Cd, Hg) are considered stable parameters.
 - DNA, drugs, antibiotics, pesticides, yeasts, bacteria are considered unstable parameters, being sensitive to temperature and dryness (degradation / change).
- Milling / grinding of materials to mechanically reduce particle size, which is accomplished by shearing, impacting and attrition using various mills, should only be considered by WP4.7., if necessary, and not in the context of this protocol.

2. Sample preparation procedure

2a. *Testing portion*

- The laboratory receives samples that has not been damaged or changed during transport and storage, and corresponds to: about **2.0 Kg x 4 (fields)**, which is representative of the batch of product.
- Roots, stalks, ears and leaves are separated with sterile gloves, as they will be analyzed independently.
- Original parts are broken into smaller parts and blended to make them more uniform in texture and consistency, and to obtain a satisfactory sized sub-sample.
- Long material, such as hay, may be cut using sterile scissors to a more appropriate length if required.
- For fine samples, coarse samples, grass or cereal silage samples and semi solid samples the sample must be well mixed using a sterile palate knife, spoon or stirring rod before sub sampling and the required portion removed using a sterile spatula or spoon and placed in a sterile container or sterile foil which is suitably identified.
- Place the **riffled, unground sample** in a sterile laboratory labeled sample bottle (or bag, etc) avoiding cross contamination; and place the other portion(s) of unground sample back in a sample bag to be retained. Label each container (bag, bottle, etc.) with the corresponding sample identifier (FED-AMR nomenclature, section D).

2b. *Composite sample*

- The test sample — i.e. the (sub-)sample prepared from the laboratory sample and from which test portions will be taken —will be 4 composite samples: one composite sample for each part of the plant (roots, stalks, ears and leaves).
- As the **composite sample** used must be representative of each parts of the plant, a small fraction should be taken from that large volume received, in such a way that the determinations will represent the mean value of the characteristic of the entire sample and taking into account the determinations to be made; thus, an equal portion from each part of the crop (roots, stalks, ears and leaves) is weighted, having at the end **at least 500 g** from each.
- From each composite sample with 500 g (4 pools) (Figure 1):
 - weight 2.75 g (in triplicate) to be used in 3 DNA extractions for metagenomics (WP2);
 - weight 2.75 g for qPCR (2.5 g for eDNA and 0.25 g for total DNA);
 - weight 55 g for bacteriology, as follows: 10 g of roots, 10 g of stalks, 10 g of ears, 25 g of leaves [see (LOP) Protocol for Microbiology: culture and identification of *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Salmonella spp*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecium/faecalis*];
 - weight 100 g to be used in quantification (WP4.7) and to stop the degradation (as they get mould very quickly and unusable), this portion should be washed with

deionised water to remove dust and soil, and then is dried in an oven at low temp (60°C) until constant weight; once they are dry they can be kept in plastic bags for storage or transport (if a freeze drier even is used, it is better); after drying the sample should have more than 50 g (up ≈ 100 g). If the laboratory do not have oven to dry crops, could be dried at room temperature as follows: cover some trays in the laboratory with filter paper, spread the plants on them and let them dry under ambient conditions, turning them occasionally until they reached constant weight. In any case, record the weight before and after drying.

- freeze at -80° C the remaining portion of the composite sample (about 364 g to 379 g).

Fig 1. Crops sampling at one time point (composite sample).

* This pool will have different quantities for Bacteriology accordingly to the part of the plant (10 g of roots, 10 g of stalks, 10 g of ears, 25 g of leaves).

2c. For the representativeness of sample

It is very important:

- to **use always** an equal amount of each of the samples for each types of pools;
- to be sure that a scale with at least two decimal-points are used, to ensure correct weighing of the required amounts;
- to **mix very well** the pooled sample, before using it for DNA extraction (WP2), or bacteriology (WP2), or quantification (WP4.7).

Note: The reliability and quality of the analysis of crops depends on the accuracy of sampling. Therefore adequate care must be taken to ensure that the analytes are handled in a way that will prevent degradation and errors.

2d. Conservation in the lab and transport

- for Bacteriology procedures (WP2): transport and conservation at 0°C to 5°C until bacteriology be processed, which must be with pooled samples [for cultivable bacteria and MICs: to be performed in each country];
- for Quantification in WP4.7: crops pool is transported in PET sterile bags, in dark.
- for Genomics (WP2): conservation at 0°C to 5°C until extraction of DNA; DNA extraction must be processed within the next 18h due to eDNA [using harmonized protocol; to be performed in each country].

3. Distribution and transport conditions for crop samples to ship

- For qPCR, WGS and metagenomics: if any country cannot perform it in the respective lab, extracted DNA should be shipped at -80°C to the receptor lab.
- For shipping samples by post to another country see conditions in Table 1 and MTA (WP1).

Table 1. Distribution and transport conditions for crop samples.

Analysis	Task	Amount	Container	Transport /Conservation until processing
Genomics (WP2)	2.3; 2.4	Extracted DNA from ≥11 g sample	Sterile tubes	Extracted DNA at -80°C
Bacteriology (WP2)	2.3	4 colonies of roots from a subculture in Nutrient agar 4 colonies of stalks 4 colonies of ears 4 colonies of leaves	Sterile tubes	Isolated colonies at -80°C
Trace elements (WP4)	4.7	More than 100 g	PET sterile bags, devoid of air	dark, cool place

4. Sample references for crop samples

Austria			
Sample Reference	Description	Type of sample	Scheduled Month
AT20-Cs-C1	Austria, crop just before harvest, crop type 1	Corn with Manure	Sep 20
AT20-Cs-C2	Austria, crop just before harvest, crop type 2	Corn with Artificial Fertilizer	Sep 20
AT20-Cs-C3	Austria, crop just before harvest, crop type 3	Corn with Manure	Sep 20
AT20-Cs-C4	Austria, crop just before harvest, crop type 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Jul 20

Estonia:			
Sample Reference	Description	Type of sample (waiting info/confirmation)	Scheduled Month
EE20-Cs-C1	Estonia, crop just before harvest, crop type 1	with Manure	Sep-20
EE20-Cs-C2	Estonia, crop just before harvest, crop type 2	with Artificial Fertilizer	Sep-20
EE20-Cs-C3	Estonia, crop just before harvest, crop type 3	Wheat with Manure	Sep-20
EE20-Cs-C4	Estonia, crop just before harvest, crop type 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Sep-20

Czech Republic:			
Sample Reference	Description	Type of sample	Scheduled Month
CZ20-Cs-C1	Czech Republic, crop just before harvest, crop type 1	Oilseed rape with Manure	Aug 20
CZ20-Cs-C2	Czech Republic, crop just before harvest, crop type 2	Oilseed rape with Artificial Fertilizer	Aug 20
CZ20-Cs-C3	Czech Republic, crop just before harvest, crop type 3	Wheat with Manure	Aug 20
CZ20-Cs-C4	Czech Republic, crop just before harvest, crop type 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Aug 20

Portugal			
Sample Reference	Description	Type of sample	Scheduled Month
PT21-Cs-C1	Portugal, crop just before harvest, crop type 1	Corn with Manure	Apr 21
PT21-Cs-C2	Portugal, crop just before harvest, crop type 2	Corn with Artificial Fertilizer	Apr 21
PT21-Cs-C3	Portugal, crop just before harvest, crop type 3	Wheat with Manure	Apr 21
PT21-Cs-C4	Portugal, crop just before harvest, crop type 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Apr 21

D. References:

- Commission Regulation (EC) No 152/2009. (2009). Laying down the methods of sampling and analysis for the official control of feed. Official Journal of the European Union, L 54/1-L 54/130.
- EN ISO 6498:2012. (2012). Animal Feeding Stuffs – Guidelines for Sample Preparation. 2012.

- FAO. (2013). *Quality assurance for microbiology in feed analysis laboratories*, by R.A. Cowie. Edited by Harinder P.S. Makkar. FAO Animal Production and Health Manual No. 16. Rome.
- Malomo GA, Ihegwuagu NE. (2017). Some Aspects of Animal Feed Sampling and Analysis, Ideas and Applications Toward Sample Preparation for Food and Beverage Analysis, Mark T. Stauffer, IntechOpen, DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.70856.
- Zhou SY, Zhu D, Giles M, Yang XR, Daniell T, Neilson R, Zhu YG. (2019). Phyllosphere of staple crops under pig manure fertilization, a reservoir of antibiotic resistance genes. *Environ Pollut*, 252(Pt A): 227-235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2019.05.098>